

TRAC-MOVE Checklist

Transparent reporting of accelerometer-based prediction models for 24-hour movement behaviour analysis.

Version 1.0.0

Concept DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18701280>

Instructions: Tick items that are fully addressed in the manuscript and report the page number where each item is addressed.

Note: “Correlates with” maps TRAC-MOVE items to established reporting checklists (TRIPOD+AI¹, STARD-AI², and Clevenger³). Parentheses indicate item numbers within each checklist.

Done	Topic	Item	Checklist item	Correlates with	Reported on page number
	Data acquisition				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Participants and ethics	1	State the number of participants, eligibility criteria, demographics (sex, age, health status, ethnicity), and recruiting strategy. Report ethics approval or justify why approval was not required.	TRIPOD+AI (6a, 6b, 20a); STARD-AI (6, 7, 8); Clevenger (3)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Wearable device	2	State the device model, brand, and wear location. If a specific device orientation is required, report how this was ensured.	TRIPOD+AI (5a); STARD-AI (13); Clevenger (8, 9)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Accelerometer sensor specifications	3	State the accelerometer sensor and brand where available, or at minimum the sampling rate, full-scale range, and bit-resolution. Report any resampling.	TRIPOD+AI (5a); STARD-AI (13); Clevenger (10)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Criterion measure	4	Specify the criterion measure (e.g., indirect calorimetry, polysomnography), equipment used, calibration or standardising procedures, synchronisation with wearable device, and scoring or calculation methods.	TRIPOD+AI (5a); STARD-AI (16); Clevenger (4)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study setting	5	State the location where the study took place (laboratory, gym, track, home, sleep clinic, hospital, free-living).	TRIPOD+AI (6a); Clevenger (1)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study structure	6	State the test protocol structure and the degree of participant autonomy during testing.	Clevenger (2)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Study activities	7	Report the activity set for training and testing, including number of activities or classes, duration, order, and any methods used to address class imbalance.	TRIPOD+AI (13); Clevenger (6)	
	Accelerometer processing decisions				
<input type="checkbox"/>	Signal quality control	8	Describe signal calibration and quality control checks, including any visual inspection, sensor calibration procedures, non-wear detection, or data-loss checks.	TRIPOD+AI (7); Clevenger (12)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Digital filter	9	State digital filtering choices, including filter type, order, and cut-off frequency or passband. If no filter was used, specify treatment of the gravity (static) component of the signal.	Clevenger (13)	

□	Accelerometer window length and use	10	State the window length (epoch) and whether windows are overlapping or non-overlapping.	Clevenger (15)	
Prediction model training/development					
□	Model inputs	11	Describe the feature set, including time-domain and frequency-domain features, and state the final model inputs after any feature selection.	Clevenger (16)	
□	Model	12	Specify the prediction model type, model-building steps, and internal validation method. If evaluating an existing model, cite the original study and describe any modifications.	TRIPOD+AI (12c); STARD-AI (15)	
□	Model output	13	Specify model outputs. For classifiers, define all classes and class definitions. For association models, state the continuous outcome and units.	TRIPOD+AI (15); Clevenger (18)	
Prediction model testing/validation					
□	Validation type	14	Specify validation type (apparent, hold-out, cross-validation, external). For cross-validation, report how folds were created and any hyperparameter tuning strategy.	Clevenger (5); STARD-AI (18)	
□	Data sources: training vs testing	15	Describe training and testing data sources separately. Report differences between training and testing data, including population, device, environment, and protocol differences.	TRIPOD+AI (12a); STARD-AI (11)	

References

- Collins, G. S. et al. TRIPOD+AI statement: updated guidance for reporting clinical prediction models that use regression or machine learning methods. *BMJ* **385**, e078378 (2024).
- Sunderajah, V. et al. The STARD-AI reporting guideline for diagnostic accuracy studies using artificial intelligence. *Nature Medicine* **31**, 3283-3289 (2025).
- Clevenger, K. A., Montoye, A. H. K., Van Camp, C. A., Strath, S. J. & Pfeiffer, K. A. Methods for estimating physical activity and energy expenditure using raw accelerometry data or novel analytical approaches: a repository, framework, and reporting guidelines. *Physiol Meas* **43**, (2022).